

THE UNIQUE CHARACTERISTICS OF ALISHER NAVOI'S LYRICS.

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Annotation. This article is about commenting on Alisher Navoi's lyrics. The work of Hazrat Alisher Navoi for the development of our culture, the care for the education of young talents is still very important and exemplary.

Key words: Lyrics by Alisher Navoi, "Khazain ul-Maoni", "Garaib us-sigar" sofa, "Ilk sofa", rubai, 16 different genres, tuuk, fard masnavi..

Alisher Navoi is a great personality who shaped a whole era in the history of consciousness and thinking of our people, artistic culture, an incomparable representative of our national literature, an immortal artist of words, who glorified the pride and honor of our people to the whole world. In other words, there is not a single person in the world who speaks Turkish and Persian, who would not know Navoi, who would not love Navoi, who would not look at Navoi with devotion and faith. Navoi is the sultan of poets, the jeweler of our native language and the gardener of our literary garden. Indeed. The work of Alisher Navoi can be compared with a boundless ocean, in the depths of ocean there are still countless treasures, although hundreds of scientific works have been made based on his works, but we have not been able to completely conquer the world of Navoi. When studying his heritage, you can always discover something new. Take, for example, the art of Navoi. Studying each verse requires a lot of research. Here is one of his famous lines:

Yuzida mehrni ko'rub o'lsam,ey, rafiq meni

Gulob ila yuv-u ,gul bargidan kafan qilg'il.

At first glance, the verses are clear and fluent, but what does Alisher Navoi want to say with this verse? This verse has a universal meaning. Alisher Navoi's ability to select and use words, philosophy in Navoi's poetry, religious and educational views of Navoi, Navoi and world literature... New aspects can be discovered in these directions.

Watching the ghazals in the work of Alisher Navoi "Khazain ul Ma'ani", "Garaib us-sigar" the first divan, we become witnesses to the fact that the following ghazals, popular among the people today, were created in the early period of the poet's work;

Kecha kelgumdur debon ul sarvi gulro' kelmadi,

Ko'zlarimg'a kecha tong otquncha uyqu kelmadi...

Ko'rgali husningni zor-u muftalo bo'ldim sango,

Ne balolig' kun edikim ,oshno bo'ldim sango...

The fact that the radifil ghazal "Ango", which is of great importance in the philosophical thought of Navoi, came from this sofa, testifies to the high potential of the poet of that time.

We see the matla of the ghazal:

Har gadokim, bo'ryoyi faqr erur kisvat ango

Saltanat zarboftidin hojat emas xil'at ango

The works of Hazrat Alisher Navoi were translated by many scholars, among them the skillful translator of ghazals Alisher Navoi, the famous writer and poet B. Seytakov, who was able to embody the artistic component of the original. In the lyrical heritage of the poet there is such a verse:

Men qachon dedim: "Vafo qilg'il mango" zulum aylading,
Sen qachon deding: "Fido bo'lg'il mango" bo'ldim sango.

The translator creatively approached the text, simplified the question-answer of the lyrical hero without spoiling the content, omitted the quotation marks and dressed it in a form understandable to the Turkmen reader. This method is used in translation practice, and there are enough examples of its good results.

Most of the ghazals in the divans of Hazrat Alisher Navoi consist of five to seven verses. In it, the larger gazelles from Ilk Divan are given in the form of khambesh or seven-stanza, that is, they are abbreviated. Mustad from Devon:

Ey, husnungga zarrayi jahon ichra tajalli, mazhar sanga ashyo,
Sen lutf bila kavnu makon ichida mavli, olam sanga mavlo

starts with a stanza. Later, this mustazad was included in the first official sofa of the poet "Badayi ul-Bidaya" and "Khazain ul-Maoni".

Alisher Navoi created a large collection of 15th-century lyrics "Khazain ul Maoniy", which contains almost all Uzbek poems belonging to 16 different genres, created by the great poet throughout his life. Choosing sources for poetic works, Navoi sincerely sought to fully and vividly express the remarkable events and hadiths of life, first of all, the essence of the subject of the image.

Alisher Navoi never neglected the ghazals, and his life impressions and reflections found their poetic expression directly in this genre.

So, throughout the entire creative activity of Alisher Navoi, the ghazal was in a "dominant" position compared to other lyrical genres. Being in this leading position is considered the highest rank in terms of numbers (2600) and content, which has not yet been discovered. Ghazals and rubais of Navoi, in a word, using 16 different genres of our literature, have created a huge heritage that can become a support for many scientists in their scientific research. After all, respect for the genius of Mir Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the world of property, feelings of pride and pride, transferred to the hearts from his image and his works, begin to glow in every heart.

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